

EFFECTIVENESS OF INFORMATION SUPPORT IN FORMING PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCES OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18517056>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th February 2026

Accepted: 06th February 2026

Online: 07th February 2026

KEYWORDS

*digital transformation, future
teacher, pedagogical
competence, information
support, digital learning
environment, educational
analytics, individual trajectory*

ABSTRACT

The thesis is based on the effectiveness of information support in the process of forming pedagogical competencies of future teachers in the conditions of digital transformation. The research methodology combines systemic and competency-based approaches and proposes a model aimed at managing the individual learning trajectory. The model includes diagnostic, guiding, resourceful and reflexive-analytical functions, which ensures the continuous development of the teacher's professional skills.

Introduction: Digital transformation requires not only the introduction of technologies in the education system, but also a reinterpretation of the content, tools and results of the teacher's professional activity. For future teachers, this situation, along with traditional methodological training, requires the formation of competencies such as pedagogical decision-making in a digital environment, adapting teaching based on the digital footprint of students, checking the reliability of information, and adhering to copyright and academic integrity standards. The concept of information support is considered not just the provision of information or the presentation of electronic resources, but rather an integrative mechanism that manages pedagogical competencies, provides a personalized and reflexive learning process based on diagnostics and analysis.

1. A systematic approach considers information support as a structural element of the educational environment, allowing to identify the connection between its components of purpose, content, means, communication and result.

2. A competency-based approach focuses on the professional actions of the future teacher and emphasizes the need for information flows and digital resources to enhance these actions.

Functions of information support

1. Diagnostic function: identifying the level of preparation and competence gaps of the future teacher; using tests, micro-teaching, case analysis, lesson development expertise and reflective diaries.

2. Guiding function: forming an individual learning trajectory - determining which topics, methods and digital tools need to be used.

3. Resource function: providing reliable and didactically appropriate content in a digital environment; resources are selected according to the criteria of quality, updating, methodological value and practical application.

4. Reflective-analytical function: evaluating one's own activities, understanding mistakes, planning further actions; pedagogical interpretation of the results of educational analytics. When these functions work as a periodically recurring cycle, the continuity of competence development is ensured.

Efficiency criteria: Since the formation of pedagogical competencies is multidimensional, the criteria include the following:

- Cognitive: theoretical basis
- Operational: ability to perform methodological actions
- Communicative: organization of dialogue and cooperation
- Reflexive: self-analysis
- Digital ethics and information culture

The scientific novelty of the thesis is that a model of managed information support is proposed for the formation of pedagogical competencies of future teachers in the conditions of digital transformation.

Entry level: initial digital literacy, pedagogical motivation, methodological preparation, resource capabilities of the educational environment.

Process level: diagnostics, individual guidance, resourcing, reflexive analysis and replanning.

Result level: growth of competencies, quality of lesson design, accuracy of assessment, flexibility of student support strategies, purposeful use of digital tools. The model does not fundamentally put the platform at the center; on the contrary, the platform and analytics are used as instruments for solving the pedagogical task.

Conclusion: The effectiveness of information support in the formation of pedagogical competencies of future teachers in the conditions of digital transformation is determined by the fact that its diagnostic, guidance, resource and reflexive-analytical functions work as a single cycle. The proposed model guides the individual trajectory of the future teacher based on evidence and increases the skills of interpreting information in the digital environment in a pedagogical sense. As a result, the use of digital tools does not remain at the level of technical skills, but rather serves a didactic purpose..

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